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СОЛИҚ ВА СОЛИҚҚА ТОРТИШ ЙЎНАЛИШИ МУТАХАССИСЛАРИГА ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ УСУЛЛАРИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада солиқ ва солиққа тортиш йўналишида тахсил олаётган талабаларга инглиз тилини ўқитишни замонавий усулларидан фойдаланиш баён этилган. Солиқ мутахассислари учун рақамли иқтисодиётни ривожлантириш шароитида халқаро тажрибадан самарали фойдаланиш орқали миллий солиқ тизимини такомиллаштиришда инглиз тилини аҳамияти ва зарурияти ёритилган. Шунингдек, мақолада ўқитувчи ва талабаларни дарс жараёнида ўзаро муносабатини ривожлантиришни, талабаларни мустақил фикрлашини, ўз фикрларини эркин баён этишни, уларда баҳслашиш маданиятини шакллантиришда муҳим рол ўйнайдиган ўқитиш усулларини қўллаш ҳақида сўз юритилган.

Калит сўзлар. Рақамли иқтисодиёт, ўқитиш усуллари, ахборот технологиялари, педагогик технология, солиқлар, ўқитувчи, талаба, мустақил таълим.

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДИКИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ В СФЕРЕ НАЛОГИ И НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается использование современных методик обучения английскому языку студентов, обучающихся в сфере налогов и налогообложения. Подчеркнута важность и необходимость владения английским языком в совершенствовании национальной налоговой системы за счет эффективного использования международного опыта в условиях развития цифровой экономики для специалистов в области налогообложения. В статье также рассматривается развитие взаимодействия учителя и ученика на уроке, использование методов обучения, которые играют важную роль в формировании у учащихся самостоятельного мышления, свободного выражения своего мнения, культуры дискуссии.

Ключевые слова. Цифровая экономика, методика обучения, информационные технологии, педагогические технологии, налоги, учитель, ученик, самостоятельное образование

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MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF TAXES AND TAXATION

ANNOTATION

The article discusses the use of modern methods of teaching English to students studying in the field of taxes and taxation. Accentuated the importance and necessity of English language proficiency in improving the national tax system through the effective use of international experience in the context of the development of the digital economy for tax professionals. The article also discusses the development of teacher-student interaction in the classroom, the use of teaching methods, which plays an important role in shaping students' independent thinking, free expression of their opinions, and a culture of discussion.

Keywords. Digital economy, teaching methods, information technologies, pedagogical technologies, taxes, teacher, student, independent education.

In developed countries, practical work is being done to digitize the economy and accelerate the process of digital transformation in order to achieve competitive positions in the developing digital space of the new world economy. In order for our country to become one of the most economically developed countries in the world today, it must first of all make great strides in the field of advanced information and communication, Internet and digital technologies, information services, advanced digital economy and training of qualified personnel.

The digital economy is one of the main indicators of the country's national economic security and independence, which will increase people's living standards several times. In today's rapidly developing digital economy in our country, one of the urgent tasks is to train personnel with modern knowledge in the system of higher education in the field of taxes and taxation. The key to these issues is to teach these students English language.

Proficiency in English is increasingly becoming a default requirement for employers. This means that if you cannot communicate in a foreign language, you will not be able to apply for a highly paid position, lose many career prospects, and miss out on your dream job. The world has changed markedly in recent decades, and knowledge of foreign languages is becoming an urgent need in it, and English, as you know, is one of the most frequently studied. And the more people who want to study it, the newer methods appear, so everyone can find the best solution for themselves.

Methodology in a general sense means a set of means and methods of teaching. One prefers to learn independently, the other is more comfortable with outside help and control.

A foreign language teaching methodology is a set of approaches, modern educational technologies and methods that include the process of learning a foreign language.

In practice through the development of foreign language teaching methods in higher education institutions, it prepares students for a thorough theoretical and practical basis for future professional activities, and develops skills and competencies for students to effectively apply their knowledge.

This, in turn, formulates students as a qualified specialist, competent, fluent in their profession and ready for constant professional growth, social and professional mobility.

As a result of the rapid implementation of modern information and pedagogical technologies in the educational process, great changes have taken place in the study of foreign languages.

As a result of the introduction of modern teaching methods and the widespread use of audio and video materials in the educational process, a process has emerged that differs sharply from the classical method of learning a foreign language.

Extensive use of innovative teaching tools and methods in the educational process today requires foreign language teachers to develop skills in the combination of traditional and modern teaching methods and tools.

In the process of improving foreign language teaching methods, teachers are required to use a wide range of interactive pedagogical methods in teaching English perfectly in order to ensure that students independently acquire new knowledge and skills in a timely manner through the Internet or other sources of information. Every English teacher usually chooses a teaching method that takes into account the students theoretical knowledge based primarily on their experience in teaching English. In practice, various pedagogical technologies of teaching English by teachers are widely used. Including practical lessons, presentations, video lessons, discussions, questions and answers, etc. Of course, the various pedagogical technologies used by teachers allow students to communicate freely, develop oral speech, develop listening and comprehension skills, and develop writing and reading skills.

Consider some of the popular modern methods of the teaching English language - how they differ and why everyone needs to choose the right option, depending on individual characteristics, the goal, time and financial resources:

Grammar translation method

Grammar Translation is a traditional, classical technique used since the end of the 19th century.

The grammar-translation method is based on the following tasks:

- study of grammar rules;
- vocabulary expansion;
- translations of texts, work with a dictionary.

Studying under such a program has its pros and cons. Of the positive qualities: effective assimilation of the grammatical basis with an intensive expansion of vocabulary. Disadvantage of the method: lack of language practice.

Direct Method

The Direct Method appeared in the early 1990s. The program is based on the regular practice of speaking and is aimed at effective language acquisition with a deep understanding of English in any everyday situation. Training involves conducting group classes of several people. In schools where the direct method English course is practiced, classes are divided into 2-3 groups.

The advantage of the technique is a good understanding of speech, conversational English skills. But with grammatical basics there may be some problems.

Audiolingual method

The audiolingual approach to learning foreign languages allows students not only to be active in the classroom, but also to develop their own practical skills independently. The uniqueness of this method is that the teacher effectively manages the lesson process and monitors the level of mastery of the topic by each student.

The importance of the method is that students are always in the process of communicating. This communication includes tasks such as listening to songs and watching movies in English, and talking to foreign nationals. Using this method of learning a foreign language, students' speech is formed and helps to express their thoughts in English.

The basis is the auditory perception of foreign speech in combination with the analogy method used when memorizing new words: the student memorizes basic vocabulary and frequently occurring language structures, which makes it easier to build sentences on their own in the future. The approach involves dividing the lesson by duration as 1 to 3: 25% of the time for theory, 75% for practice. Dialogues on various topics with a gradual expansion of vocabulary, starting from the basic set.

The methodology is also good as a group option, including for preparing for exams, and is used by universities in many countries, including Oxford.

Communicative Language Teaching method

The basis is conversational practice, diverse communication in the target language, which allows you to overcome the notorious language barrier with surprising ease.

Combines:

- communication in English from the very first lesson, even for language learners "from scratch";
- the use of excellently crafted teaching aids, the material of which can be successfully applied in everyday life.

It is on this approach that training programs with native speakers are based.

The technique eliminates the cramming of grammar rules, replacing the memorization of the rules with their repeated practical application, and provides knowledge of a foreign language at the level of a second native.

Learning through reading method

The basis is reading specially adapted literature, learning in a light mode, which is well suited for beginners. This passive method is remarkable in that the process is based on an exciting reading and does not involve doing exercises: associative thinking allows our brain to assimilate new material, it only provides additional efficiency to the process.

This, of course, is not about reading English-speaking authors in the original. The training built according to this technique is a thoughtful combination of an adapted text and an interlinear translation of another language with transcription and clarification of individual words. This type of learning excludes the development of skills and is based on involvement and novelty of impressions.

Self-learning method

Due to low financial resources and lack of time, various professions and students try to learn English independently. Today, there is an opportunity to use various online learning resources available on social networks to learn English independently. In our opinion, in order to learn English independently, the listener must have a desire to learn the language, a willingness to work independently, and an effective way of learning the language.

As you can see, the methods presented vary, depending on the circumstances and opportunities available to the teacher or students, and the choice of the most appropriate and effective method. In practice, there are cases when the methods are used in combination. The main goal is to arouse the desire of professionals to learn English and to form the necessary theoretical and practical skills for the use of English in practice.

Achieving this goal will allow the country to fill the taxes and taxation sector with qualified personnel, which will create the basis for effective tax policy.

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